

How to write a GDPR PRIVACY NOTICE in Diamond Open Access publishing

Do you handle EU residents' data ?

If so, GDPR applies to you.

You need a clear privacy notice explaining how you process and protect their data. Here's how.

#1 Make it easy to read and understand

Articles 12, 13, and 14 of the GDPR provide guidance on creating these notices, emphasising clarity and accessibility.

Privacy notices should be in plain language, delivered promptly, and provided free of charge.

- Avoid vague qualifiers: *may, might, sometimes, often* → *will, always*.
- Provide clear, specific explanations: *We will retain your personal details* → *We will retain your name, email address and institution name*.
- Write in active tense with well-structured sentences.
- Use a spelling and grammar checker to keep sentences short and clear.

#2 Provide every information required

- The organisation's identity, contact details, and those of its data.
- Protection Officer, if there is one, or the individual responsible for monitoring and implementing the guidelines of the GDPR).
- Purpose and legal basis for data processing.
- Legitimate interests of the organisation or third party.
- Recipients or categories of recipients.
- Details of any data transfers to third countries.
- Retention period or criteria for determining it.
- Details of the data subject's rights.
- Right to withdraw consent .
- Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.
- Automated decision-making systems, including profiling.
- *If data is collected directly from individuals*: Whether the provision of personal data is part of a statutory or contractual requirement or obligation and the possible consequences of failing to provide the personal data.
- *If data is collected via another organisation or service*: The categories of personal data obtained.

#3 Share it

- **On your website** under the title "Privacy Policy" with a direct link from each page.
- **Orally upon request** via the Data Protection Officer.

More info

Best practices

- The EU website for GDPR offers a section on best practices for writing a compliant privacy notice, including a template.
<https://gdpr.eu/privacy-notice/>,

References

- European Commission. General Data protection Regulation.
<https://gdpr.eu/tag/gdpr/>
- European Commission. Writing a GDPR-compliant privacy notice, template included. <https://gdpr.eu/privacy-notice/>